

**BIORemediation systems exploiting SYnergies
for improved removal of Mixed pOllutants**

Deliverable D3.2

**Intermediate report on aggregated and immobilized consortia
and biofilms - Outline**

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Executive Summary

In this intermediate deliverable we reported results of activities that are the basis for further work on the spatial structuring of bacterial communities that were obtained within the scope of T1.3 activities. In this regards, within the activities under the T3.2 JSI was focused in developing methods for spatial structuring of multicellular structures, involving bacterial strains organized as aggregates or attached on inert surfaces. Meanwhile, LEITAT was concentrated on engineering BES for (i) metal precipitation, (ii) the degradation of hydrocarbons and (iii) degradation of chlorinated ethenes. As a result of T3.2 activities till this report, JSI developed various methods and determined limiting parameters for efficient construction of synthetic polymicrobial structures using model organisms and simulating physical conditions that are expected in natural conditions such as in rhizosphere, water flow systems and electrodes in BES systems. In contrast, LEITAT has been focused in BES systems where after designing the bioelectrochemical approach that will be aimed to be used in WP4 for each target pollutant from polluted samples selected in task 1.2, LEITAT has defined the protocols to grow the biomass according to the BES design requirements in each of the above mentioned pollutant cases. These protocols for obtaining biomass in BES systems are based on the microorganisms selection by electrodes potential modulation to inoculate the reactors. Additionally, different inoculation reactors have been designed and constructed in the framework of T3.2.2 following the specific aims fulfilling degradation of selected pollutants. The developed protocols are being applied and the reactors inoculation is ongoing. The biomass obtained in this step will be used in task 4.4 for the removal of targeted pollutants. Based on the current knowledge obtained during the activities in both subtasks further steps will be proceeded to bring on one hand isolated consortia and strains within the BIOSYSMO project to the systems that will be used in the WP4 activities either as synthetic communities attached on rhizosphere, carriers or on optimized BES electrode and on other hands the prepared synthetic communities will be then further investigated under the activities related to the WP2 in order to determine metabolic activities and spatially related interspecies collaborations.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
Table of Contents.....	4
List of Figures.....	6
List of Tables.....	7
Table of Abbreviations.....	8
1 Introduction.....	9
2 Subtask 3.2.1 - Design of the consortia with microgeographic placement.....	11
2.1 Approaches for construction and manipulation of 3D structures and determining their stability and succession.....	11
2.1.1 Methodology.....	11
2.1.2 Results.....	13
2.2 Methods for engineering and manipulation of planar microbial structures.....	19
2.2.1 Impact of Combination of Biological and Physical Properties.....	19
2.2.1.1 Methodology.....	19
2.2.1.2 Results.....	20
2.2.2 Impact of hydrophilicity on the biomass attachment.....	22
2.2.2.1 Methodology.....	23
2.2.2.2 Results.....	23
3 Subtask 3.2.2 - Development of electroactive biofilms.....	25
3.1 Preparing electrogenic core-shell structures from microbial consortia by aggregation.....	25
3.1.1 Methodology.....	25
3.1.2 Results.....	26
3.2 Estimating suitability of using polyelectrolytes for deposition of cells on electrodes.....	30
3.2.1 Methodology.....	31
3.2.2 <i>Results</i>	31
3.3 Design of the custom-made BES setup.....	32
3.4 Modulation of redox potential on electrodes.....	33
3.4.1 Biofilm for metals removal.....	33
3.4.1.1. Methods.....	34
3.4.1.2. Results.....	35

3.4.2. Biofilms for HC removal.....	37
3.4.1.1. Methods.....	37
3.4.1.2. Results.....	37
3.4.3. Biofilms for Chlorinated Ethenes removal.....	38
3.4.3.1. Methods.....	38
3.4.3.2. Results.....	39
4 Conclusions.....	40
5 Planned work for the second period.....	41
6 References.....	42

List of Figures

Figure 1.....	14
Figure 2.....	16
Figure 3.....	17
Figure 4.....	18
Figure 5.....	19
Figure 6.....	21
Figure 7.....	21
Figure 8.....	22
Figure 9.....	24
Figure 10.....	24
Figure 11.....	26
Figure 12.....	26
Figure 13.....	27
Figure 14.....	28
Figure 15.....	29
Figure 16.....	30
Figure 17.....	32
Figure 18.....	32
Figure 19.....	33
Figure 20.....	33
Figure 21.....	34
Figure 22.....	35
Figure 23.....	36
Figure 24.....	36
Figure 25.....	38

List of Tables

Table 1.....	20
Table 2.....	25

Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
BES-M	Bioelectrochemical system for metals removal
ORR	Oxygen Reduction Reaction
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
CV	Cyclic Voltammetry
BES	Bioelectrochemical System
HC	Hydrocarbons
BES-HC	Bioelectrochemical system for hydrocarbon removal
TPH	Total petroleum hydrocarbons
BTEX	Benzene Toluene Ethylene Xylene
PAH	Polyaromatic Hydrocarbons
MEC	Microbial Electrolysis Cell
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
OHRB	Organohalide respiring bacteria
PCE	Perchloroethylene
TCE	Trichloroethylene
VC	Vinyl chloride
GC	Gas chromatography
ECD	Electron capture detection
PE	Polyelectrolyte
PAA-HCL	Poly(allylamine hydrochloride)
PEI	Polyethyleneimine
AcetPEI	Acetylated polyethyleneimine
PSS	Poly(sodium 4-styrenesulfonate)
MIC	Minimal Inhibitory Concentration
LB	Lysogeny broth media
M9	Minimal media
OD	Optical density
FSC	Forward Scattered light
MQw	Ultrapure water
DPC	Diphenylcarbazine
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
EDS	Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
ROI	Region of Interests
NB	Nutrient Broth media
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
ELS	Electrophoretic Light Scattering
FITC	Fluorescein isothiocyanate
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
PZC	Point of Zero Charge
FTO	Fluorine-doped Tin Oxide

1 Introduction

This deliverable provides an overview of both individual and collaborative initiatives between LEITAT and JSI aimed at enhancing biodegradation capabilities of various strains (i) individual cells, (ii) corresponding isolated consortia, the consortia and isolates obtained in the activities within T1.3, or (iii) artificially constructed synthetic consortia formed of individual isolates also isolated during the T1.3 activities and further characterized in T3.1. In the scope of activities within T3.2 the main approach that is aimed to contribute in enhancement of these strains is controlling their spatial distribution through development of methods of formation of synthetic aggregates and biofilms. The work is an integral part of the activities within the WP3 T3.2 and is separated in two subtasks: T3.2.1 with the main aim to explore effects of spatial structuring of the members of communities and is focused on intercellular interactions, and T3.2.2 where the work is focused in using the spatial distribution of cells and immobilization on electrodes for increasing biodegradation activity of Bioelectrochemical Systems (BES).

Moreover, T3.2 is connected with WP1 T1.3 where the microbial resources were obtained. Moreover, the metabolic modeling activities within the T2.2 (WP2) based on data from T3.1 (WP3) and T1.3 (WP1) is going to serve as a tool for determining the most suitable combination of strains as well as supports the further engineering of spatial distribution of cells by knowing which members of the community can work at particular conditions e.g. in the microenvironmental conditions where anaerobic and aerobic niches are formed. The methods developed within the T3.2 can also contribute to the T3.4 in enhancing the delivery of genetic material in microbial communities by forcing close interaction of cells and local sub optimal conditions (Sheppard et al., 2020) that can stimulate introduction of provided genetic material into the naive microbial community.

Approaches that were developed within this periodic report and results of testing of the performance of constructed microbial communities in synthetic polymicrobial structures will be the basis of further use of the structures and developed applications in (i) bioremediation of surface waters by placing microbes in rhizosphere of phytoremediation system for freshwater as well as in estuarine sediments, see T4.1 and T4.3 (WP4), respectively, and (ii) in T4.4 (WP4) where BES system will be used in the treatment of groundwater.

Accordingly, during this period, JSI was focused in developing methods for spatial structuring of multicellular structures, involving bacterial strains organized as aggregates or attached on inert surfaces. Meanwhile, LEITAT was concentrated on engineering BES for (i) metal precipitation, (ii) the degradation of hydrocarbons and (iii) degradation of chlorinated ethenes.

Specifically, In this interim report, JSI's primary focus revolved around two key objectives: (i) advancing methods to achieve precise control over the spatial distribution of bacterial strains and (ii) establishing methodological setups for measuring the spatial distribution of these bacterial strains. Additionally, we aimed to assess their impact on the degradation of organic pollutants or the precipitation of toxic metals. Since the synthetic biofilms are planned to be built on various substrates: (i) plant roots, (ii) carriers, and (iii) inorganic materials resembling electrodes, JSI developed methods enabling electrostatic approach for attachment of microbes on various surfaces for application that are going to be used in BIOSYSMO. Since we hypothesize that the attachment efficiencies are also dependent on the physical characteristics of cells, moreover, not only surfaces were tested, but also the contribution of physicochemical conditions of milieu in which cells are suspended and effects of intrinsic property of microbial cell shapes. In this period we did not use intensively strains and consortia obtained within the

T1.3 activities (see D1.2). However, to determine some key parameters that are contributing the attachment of cells we used model laboratory microorganisms which are easier to manipulate. In contrast to this method that is based on the random aggregation, in the subtask T3.2.1 (WP3) we developed methods for the organization of both three-dimensional and planar structures where also a new approach μ LUME was developed. Based on the electrostatic approaches two types of the physiological situations caused by the 3D structuring of microbial communities has been considered (i) preparation of the aerobic anaerobic conditions by forming aggregates and (ii) preparation of layered and 3D structures for either engineering electrogenic biofilms that will be implemented in the T3.2.2 or structuring biofilms that can be applied on plant roots or other inanimate structures and can be implemented in T3.1 activities.

For T3.2.2 JSI in cooperation with LEITAT, prepared a BES prototype that is enabling easy accessibility to the electrodes since the manipulation and biofilm succession must be monitored continuously. In such reactor it would be possible to monitor biofilm structure, succession, composition, and activity without extensive disassembly procedures. In contrast to the JSI contribution, LEITAT was focused on engineering BES approaches applying procedures for selection of electrogens by modulating the electrochemical potential of the electrodes. In WP4 LEITAT will lead the development of 3 different technologies for the removal/degradation of metals, hydrocarbons and chlorinated ethenes. In the context of WP4 the activities in T3.2.2, LEITAT have developed 3 different reactor inoculation strategies based on the role of biomass in each case:

(i) Metals removal, the objective is to achieve a biofilm capable of acting as electron donor by catalyzing the degradation of organic matter contained in a polluted stream. These electrons are used in the cathode, which is in contact with the metals polluted groundwater, to drive the metals removal by different removal pathways associated with different reduction reactions. To do that, single chamber flat-plate reactors have been designed, constructed and are being operated by modulating the electrochemical potential of the anode in order to grow the desired biofilms in different batches.

(ii) Hydrocarbon removal, the growth of weak electrogens capable to interact with solid electrodes is promoted to help indigenous microorganisms to degrade the hydrocarbons contained in the groundwater. In this case single chamber H-type reactors with air-cathode were designed and constructed. After a first biomass enrichment step (reported in D1.2) it was decided to add a second cathode strategy (liquid cathode) to the study and modify the protocol for the reactors inoculation by removing the kerosene addition.

(iii) Chlorinated ethenes abatement, the presence of *Dehalococcoides mccartyi* is reported to be a relevant factor for the reductive dechlorination, for this reason the polluted samples which have been received recently are being analyzed to detect its presence. In parallel, a microorganisms cultivation phase will be carried out and, after that, the chlorinated ethenes degraders promotion will be done in flat-plate microbial electrolysis cell.

Furthermore, the collaboration between LEITAT and JSI during this phase included two key aspects: (i) supplying electrogenic biofilm as a source for strains utilized in biofilm structuring, and (ii) sharing knowledge on the engineering of BES that was implemented at the JSI for studying spatial distribution of the members of the biofilm on the electrodes.

In the upcoming phases of this project, for T3.2.1 JSI will focus in implementation of developed methods during this period for using isolated strains and consortia from T1.3 as well as to integrate with the activities under T3.1, WP2 and WP4. For activities under T3.2.2 JSI will integrate the procedures acquired at JSI with the organisms selected from both JSI and LEITAT. This integration aims to investigate the enhancement of the BES by reducing the adaptation time of the microbial community,

analyzing community succession on the electrodes, and augmenting pollutant removal through increased process efficiencies.

2 Subtask 3.2.1 - Design of the consortia with microgeographic placement

2.1 Approaches for construction and manipulation of 3D structures and determining their stability and succession

JSI developed a protocol for the construction of bacterial aggregates using *Shewanella oneidensis* as the closest approximate to both the environmental electroactive strains as well as facultative anaerobes that can switch from aerobic to anaerobic type of metabolism. The approach involved electrostatic modification of the bacterial cell surface to study the formation of biocatalytic cores capable of both aerobic and anaerobic degradation of pollutants. We varied (i) number of layers of polyelectrolytes, (ii) charge of the outer layer and (iii) number of the layers that are coating the whole synthetically formed multicellular structure. In these conditions we tested stability and succession of the formed aggregated structures as well as formation of precipitates due to the electron flows from aerobic to anaerobic niches. Methods developed here are aimed at structuring multispecies aggregates from isolated strains reported in D1.2.

2.1.1 Methodology

Cell-Polyelectrolyte Interaction Assessment. Our study aimed to delve into the interaction between *Shewanella oneidensis* cells and a variety of polyelectrolytes, both natural and synthetic, bearing positive and negative charges. Despite prior reports indicating potential toxicity of cationic polyelectrolytes (PEs) towards bacterial cells Rybkin et al., 2019, in preparation (Rybkin et al., 2021)), the specific interaction with *S. oneidensis* remains an unexplored aspect in the existing literature.

Our initial focus involved examining the interaction of *S. oneidensis* cells with Poly(allylamine hydrochloride) (PAA-HCl, Sigma Aldrich cat no 71550-12-4), Starch (ThermoFisher cat no. 9005-84-9), branched polyethyleneimine (PEI, 600-kDa, Sigma-Aldrich cat no. 408719), and an acetylated version of PEI (AcetPEI) with reduced primary amino groups by their acetylation (modification procedure described in Deev et al., 2021). The evaluation included scrutinizing the inhibitory activities of these polyelectrolytes against bacteria.

To determine the extent of inhibition, we utilized a modified Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) test. The polymer solutions were prepared at concentrations of 2.5 mg/mL, and 90 μ l of 2X concentrated Lysogeny broth (LB) medium was added to counteract the dilution effect on nutrients. Subsequently, 20 μ l of the cell suspension with an optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600nm}) of 0.4 was added to 180 μ l of a mixture of polymer and medium.

Chronic exposure assessment involved monitoring OD_{600nm} every 30 minutes for a period of 48 hours. The incubation was carried out at 28°C, with 30 seconds of shaking preceding each measurement.

Electrostatic Modification of Cells. The construction of synthetic bacterial aggregates entailed coating bacterial cells with two types of polyelectrolytes. AcetPEI formed positive layers, and Poly(sodium 4-styrenesulfonate) (PSS) formed negative layers, following the method outlined in Rybkin et al., 2019. In brief, a bacterial suspension with $OD_{600nm} = 0.2$ was mixed with an equal amount of polyelectrolyte solution. After a five-minute vigorous vortex, centrifugation at 1200g for three minutes prevented unwanted flocculation. The pellet was washed with ultrapure water, and cells were

suspended in a 0.9% NaCl solution for preserving their viability. This process enabled to deposit a single layer of polyelectrolyte.

For additional layers, polyelectrolytes with opposite charges were used, repeating the procedure with centrifugation at 1500g for compact pellets. We applied up to three layers for positively charged cells and two layers for negatively charged cells in our study.

Aggregation Protocols Tested. We developed two protocols for constructing artificial bacterial aggregates:

(i) In the first approach, native cells were mixed with cells encapsulated in a single positive layer of AcetPEI and their optical density adjusted to $OD_{600nm} = 0.2$.

(ii) The second approach involved *S. oneidensis* cells encapsulated with 2 and 3 layers of PE, resulting in positive and negative surface charges, respectively. After incubation with PSS and centrifugation, the aggregates were resuspended in 0.9% NaCl. A positive PE layer was deposited by incubating the aggregates with AcetPEI, followed by centrifugation and resuspension.

Consistent use of a 15 mL Falcon tube with a 5 mL bacterial suspension ensured stability during mixing for reproducible aggregate synthesis. Variations in the number of PE layers resulted in different structural robustness, with aggregates from the first approach termed "weak" and those from the second approach labeled "robust."

Assessment of Aggregate Stability, Succession, and Interaction with Planktonic Cells. Physical appearance and properties of constructed aggregates were assessed using a combination of flow-cytometry and fluorescent microscopy. Using flow cytometry the Forward Scattered (FSC) light was utilized as a parameter reflecting the size and stability of constructed aggregated structures. Stability was evaluated over a 72-hour period, subjecting both types of aggregates to different cultivating conditions, including shear forces and nutrient availability.

Shear forces were simulated by constant agitation at 150rpm, and nutrient availability was regulated by the media composition: nutrient-rich Lysogeny-Broth Media (LB) or minimal media (M9) with 2% glucose as a single carbon source. Measurements were conducted by dispensing 50 μ L of the sample into 450 μ L of ultrapure water (MQw) and filtration through a 100 μ m mesh to prevent device clogging. First 100,000 events at a flow speed of 35 μ L/min and a core size of 14 μ m were recorded in each of the analyzed samples. The outcomes of tested conditions were utilized for further protocol improvement in the construction of spatially oriented structures.

Given the varied surface charge, stiffness, and cell density resulting from different protocols, the interaction of such structures with planktonic microbiota became a crucial point for a better understanding of the principles of growth and functioning. To determine the dynamics of colonization of aggregated cells by planktonic cells during the growth of bacterial aggregates, both planktonic and aggregated types of cells were stained with nucleic acid dyes Syto11 and Syto64 and incubated under different cultivating conditions. The interaction of planktonic and aggregated cells was estimated by the ratio of fluorescence intensity between them, where increased green-to-red values indicated an intensified contribution of planktonic cells in the structure of the bacterial aggregate. The estimation was performed for 0, 1, 12, 24, 48, and 144 hours of cultivation, using an inverted fluorescent microscope Zeiss Axio Observer Z1 (Zeiss, Germany), equipped with GFP (485 nm/528 nm) and dsRED filter sets (599 nm/619 nm), and the digital CCD camera Orca (Hamamatsu, Japan).

Vanadate V(V) Reduction Efficiency in Aerobic Conditions. To examine the hypothesis of anaerobic metal reduction within artificially constructed catalytic cores formed of spatially structured aggregates

where in aerobic conditions occur inside the aggregated structure, we utilized V_2O_5 as an indicator of electron transfer from organic compounds to vanadate resulting in reduction of V^{5+} to V^{4+} .

A 1% v/v inoculum of robust aggregate structures was introduced into modified minimal media enriched with 3.8mM V_2O_5 . The cultivation spanned 14 days at room temperature with continuous agitation at 160 rpm. Negative controls involved planktonic *S. oneidensis* suspensions in aerated conditions, while positive controls comprised suspensions under an anaerobic atmosphere created by a gas mixture of 10% CO_2 , 5% H_2 , and 80% N_2 within an anaerobic chamber (BakerRuskin, UK).

To evaluate reducing activity within the aggregates, a method based on the reaction of vanadate with diphenylcarbazide (DPC) under acidic conditions was employed (Carpentier et al., 2003). An assay solution was prepared by combining 1% (wt/vol) DPC in acetone with an equal volume of 2M H_2SO_4 . A 500 μ L volume of the centrifuged supernatant was mixed with an equal volume of the assay solution. Following a 15-minute incubation.

Raman Spectroscopy. Raman spectroscopy was used to investigate the potential formation of reduced vanadium (V) particles. A Raman microscope (Alpha300, WiTec GmbH, Germany) with a 785 nm NIR laser was employed for Raman spectra acquisition. Raman Spectroscopy maps (200×200 μ m) were recorded using a Nikon 4-x/0.6 NA objective, with a laser power of 3.5 mW and an integration time of 5 seconds per spectrum.

2.1.2 Results

Comparing Stability of aggregates constructed by different approaches. The analysis of the FSC light parameter provided crucial insights into the stability of the constructed bacterial aggregates under diverse cultivation conditions. Two distinct methodologies were employed in their formation: one involving native cells from the environmental samples mixed with single-layer encapsulated cells, and the other incorporating *S. oneidensis* cells encapsulated by covering cells with 2 and 3 layers of polyelectrolytes, resulting in negative and positive surface charges, respectively.

During a comprehensive 72-hour evaluation, the aggregates were exposed to varying cultivating conditions, including shear forces simulated by constant agitation at 150rpm and different nutrient availability scenarios using LB medium and M9 medium supplemented with 2% glucose. Notably, both types of aggregates exhibited a decrease in size over time when cultivated without agitation, indicating a gradual reduction of volume of the aggregates in the absence of external shear forces (Figure 1).

Under constant agitation, distinctive outcomes were observed based on the nature of the aggregates and the nutrient composition of the media. The most prominent effect on expansion of aggregates was observed in aggregates cultivated in LB medium. Weak aggregates displayed a continuous increase in size, suggesting a propensity for growth and expansion in response to agitation. In contrast, robust aggregates in the same conditions exhibited a reduction in size after 18 hours of cultivation, followed by subsequent growth.

Figure 1: Temporal evolution of bacterial aggregate sizes, differentiated by polyelectrolyte (PE) layering ("Weak" with 1 PE layer and "Robust" with 5 PE layers), is illustrated under varied cultivation conditions. Cultures were subjected to LB and M9 media supplemented with 2% glucose serving as a carbon source, while the cultivation was either subjected to the constant agitation (Agitation) or it was absent (Stationary).

Succession of aggregates and interaction with planktonic cells. Insights into the dynamics of bacterial aggregate succession and their interaction with planktonic cells were garnered through fluorescence microscopy measurements. Notably, the abundance of planktonic cells exhibited distinct patterns dependent on the cultivation conditions, highlighting a complex interplay between aggregate structures and freely suspended microbial cells.

In samples cultivated in LB media with continuous agitation, a steady increase of the presence of planktonic cells was consistently observed (Figure 2). This suggests an ongoing attachment of the cells to the surface of aggregates. In contrast, under the same nutrient conditions but without agitation, an opposing trend emerged, indicating a decline in the abundance of planktonic cells on the surface of the aggregates. This contrast underscores the influence of shear forces on the liberation of planktonic cells from the aggregates.

Conversely, in samples cultivated in minimal media (M9), trends mirrored those observed in LB media. Without agitation, a continuous rise in planktonic fluorescence was noted, indicating a gradual increase of the amount of cells on the surface of aggregates over time. However, in agitated samples, a significant increase in planktonic fluorescence occurred within the initial hour, followed by a subsequent

decrease. This dynamic pattern suggests an initial surge in planktonic cell attachment due to agitation, succeeded by a subsequent release.

Figure 2: Dynamics of succession of aggregates and interaction with planktonic cells. Fluorescent signals of planktonic and aggregated forms of *S. oneidensis* cells were used to estimate the succession of aggregates and their interaction with planktonic cells. Cultivation conditions included with or without agitation in nutrient-rich (LB) or nutrient-defined (M9) media. Non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by Wilcoxon post hoc test, was conducted, using the beginning of the experiment (0h) as the reference group for pairwise comparisons.

Estimation of vanadate V^{5+} reduction efficiency in aerobic conditions. To determine anaerobic niche formation within the synthetic aggregates and also to develop a method for selection of electrogenic active microbes we used the V^{5+} as an indicator of these two conditions, since V^{5+} can be biologically reduced only under the lowered oxygen conditions. When V^{5+} is reduced to V^{4+} it forms precipitates and the precipitates when formed within the aggregates can be observed by microscopic techniques. In addition, the solution becomes less green colored since green coloration is caused by the V^{5+} that is getting decreased due to the precipitation. Consequently, the formation of precipitates can determine where the reduction occurs in the aggregate and spectrophotometric measurements of the solution can determine the intensity of the reduction process. In our experiments, the V also served as an example of the soluble toxic metal and is simulating the environmental conditions heavily metal polluted sampling site 6. The properties for precipitation of toxic metals in the gradient between aerobic and anaerobic conditions represent as a key property for determining electrogenic microbiota and their active presence enable operation of bioelectrochemical systems. To investigate this, we chose V_2O_5 as a model pollutant, considering *Shewanella* species reported capability to reduce it in anaerobic conditions (Carpentier et al., 2003). The same method developed during this stage of the BIOSYSMO project are planned to be used for separation of electroactive and nonelectrogenic bacteria for the subtask 3.2.2.

In the experimental setup, constructed bacterial aggregates were incubated in minimal media with 2% glucose as the sole carbon source and 3.8mM V_2O_5 as the electron acceptor. The reduction of V^{5+} to V^{4+} was quantified through spectrophotometric measurements of V^{5+} absorbance. The resulting decrease in absorbance values served as an indicator of reducing activity. This efficiency within the aggregated structures was then compared to the activity of planktonic suspensions cultivated in both aerated and anaerobic conditions.

The artificial aggregates showed 1.3 times higher reducing activities than the reducing activity of the culture containing only planktonic cells (in aerated suspension) within the first 4 hours of the observation. After 24 h and 48 h this difference became even more evident (Figure 3). However, the positive control containing planktonic cells cultivated under anaerobic conditions showed more than 2 times more intensive precipitation activity, but must be noted that the activity of the aggregates was not normalized to the number of amount of cells or more precisely, to the amount of cells growing in the anaerobic niches within the aggregates.

Figure 3: The reducing activity of *S. oneidensis* cells in different states: planktonic suspension cultivated aerobically, spatially-oriented bacterial aggregates cultivated aerobically, and control that represents the planktonic suspension cultivated anaerobically. The precipitation activity was calculated from the decreased values of the absorbance of the dissolved V_5^+ signal and normalized to the abiotic control.

Spatial distribution of V precipitates. Since we determined that aggregates form precipitates in aerobic conditions we hypothesize that these precipitates are formed in the centre of the aggregate. If this can be proven this can have two implications: (i) the proposed method can be used for determining electroactivity of isolated strains or consortia and (ii) the formation of the synthetic aggregates can be used in aerobic precipitation of toxic metals in heavily polluted water or soil ecosystems. By using two

approaches on one hand Raman spectroscopy combined with spatial resolution using confocal microscopy and on other hand by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) together with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) detectors for determining spatially distributed elemental composition, we sought to characterize the grown aggregates of *S. oneidensis*.

Figure 4: Distribution of V particles (upper panel) and organic biomass (lower panel) in artificial aggregates based on overnight map scanning using Raman spectroscopy

To be able to perform these two imaging and spectroscopy techniques on our samples we improved lyophilization protocol enabling preservation of the physical integrity of the aggregates. The Raman spectroscopy analysis of the lyophilized aggregates revealed two characteristic peaks at 858 and 1280 cm^{-1} (Figure 4). The presence of the 858 cm^{-1} peak is indicative of a vanadium polymorph, presumably potassium metavanadate (Baddour-Hadjean et al., 2014). Concurrently, the 1280 cm^{-1} peak is consistent with carbon atoms. The spatial distribution of these peaks across the aggregates, as depicted in Region of Interests (ROI) maps (Figure 4, upper panel), provides insights into the localization of vanadium precipitates.

The observed distribution pattern suggests a concentration of vanadium precipitates closer to the center of the aggregate, where the sample exhibits maximal thickness. This central region, characterized by reduced oxygen availability, offers the most appropriate environment for anaerobic respiration by bacterial cells.

To further validate these findings, SEM coupled with EDS provided additional insights. The SEM images distinctly revealed the formation of solid nanoparticles within one of the aggregates (refer to Figure 5, SEM).

Figure 5: SEM image of bacterial aggregate (a) and V-nanoparticle (b) with corresponding EDS maps

2.2 Methods for engineering and manipulation of planar microbial structures

In BES systems in order to increase efficiencies various types of electrodes with very high surfaces are used. Moreover, the microorganisms associated with plants are also attached on root surfaces. Both of these two cases, one inanimate and another plant surface, are representing planar surfaces which are going to be modified by synthetically structured microbial biofilms. Therefore, during this work, we determined how surface properties such as (i) roughness, (ii) the type of roughness and (iii) rheological properties of the liquid flow around the surfaces affects the passive attachment of variously shaped microbes. These measurements are prerequisites to determine the most suitable conditions for the formation and preserving of the spatially structured synthetic biofilms and also determine at which conditions the formation of synthetic biofilms can outperform the natural attachment process.

2.2.1 Impact of Combination of Biological and Physical Properties

According to our previous publication (Deev et al., 2021) the surface structure as well as the type of the bacterial strain, especially their shapes, are the most important parameters for efficient formation of artificial structures, here we further determined physical parameters that determine their attachment. As bacterial attachment is a complex process involving both physical and biological aspects of cell-surface interaction, the thorough investigation of these factors is crucial for understanding the features of biofilm formation. Our methodology incorporated a comprehensive analysis, considering not only the environmental factors such as the speed of water flow, ionic strength of the solution, and surface roughness but also delving into the morphological variations of attached bacteria.

2.2.1.1 Methodology

For the prediction of the efficiencies of the attachment of bacteria with various shapes to surfaces, four model strains were used: *E. coli* top10 emGFP, *E. coli* MG1655, *S. epidermidis* DSM20044, and *S. epidermidis* BH1. To determine the above mentioned effects, strain selection was based on their distinct morphologies and biofilm-forming abilities (Table 1). Based on these information the same characteristics will be firstly determined for the selected pollutant degrading strains obtained within the WP1 T1.3 activities and then on a basis of insights represented on these model organisms the most optimal approach can be applied to build the most robust synthetic multicellular structures.

Model bacteria were cultivated for 48-hours at 37°C in liquid Nutrient Broth media (NB), followed by harvesting and washing at 5000g (Sigma 4-16K, Germany) for 5 minutes using either MQw or 0.9%

NaCl. The final optical density (OD_{600nm}) for each experiment was adjusted to 0.1±0.005. Staining with Syto11 (Invitrogen) was performed according to the commercial protocol, with a final working solution concentration of 10 µM.

Table 1: The growth conditions and biological characteristics of the selected bacterial strains. “+” and “-” indicate the ability and disability, respectively, to form biofilms based on data available in this study (**) or elsewhere (*).

Strain	Morphology	Biofilm formation	Reference
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> DSM 20044	Cocci	+++*	(Dice et al., 2009)
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> BH1	Cocci	-**	(Kurečič et al., 2018)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> TOP10	Rod-shaped	-*	(Cowan et al., 2001)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> MG1655	Rod-shaped	+++*	(Sung et al., 2006)

Characterization of the selected strains included an assessment of surface properties such as zeta-potential and electrophoretic mobility, utilizing the electrophoretic light scattering technique as detailed by Rybkin et al., 2019 (Figure 6). To study the impact of surface properties, silica (SiO₂) wafers with varying pore depths (0, 30, 55, 135, 180, 260, and 550 nm) were employed (see Figure 7a), and their characterization and surface property determination were conducted using scanning electron microscopy and interferometry methods.

Following characterization, wafers were mounted in a specially designed cultivation chamber (Figure 7 b). Prior to each experiment, wafers underwent sonication in an ultrasound bath and cleaning with isopropanol, acetone, and ethanol. To simulate liquid flow, assembled chambers were immersed in a container with bacterial culture at a 90-degree angle and moved along the X-axis at constant speeds of F18, F37, F75, F150, and F300 revolutions per minute for one hour. Unattached cells were carefully washed with MQw or 0.9% NaCl. To prevent wafer drying, a few droplets of liquid were added, and chambers were sealed with coverslips.

The investigation of bacterial attachment was conducted using an inverted fluorescent microscope (Zeiss Axio Observer Z1, Zeiss, Germany). Fluorescently-labeled cells were observed through a green filter set (485/528 nm), and images were captured using the digital CCD camera Orca (Hamamatsu, Japan). The number of attached cells was determined from the obtained images, using the FIJI software (Deev et al., 2021). Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed using the FactoMineR package for data analysis and the factoextra package for data visualization (KASSAMBARA, 2017; Lê et al., 2008).

2.2.1.2 Results

Figure 6: Measured zeta potential (left) and electrophoretic mobility (right) of strains used in the research.

The examination of bacterial strains employed in the study unveiled distinctive cell surface properties. Notably, cocci-shaped strains exhibited similar values for both electrophoretic mobility and zeta potential. In contrast, a notable 5-fold difference was observed among *E. coli* strains, as illustrated in Figure 6. This divergence in surface properties underscores the varied nature of bacterial strains, emphasizing the importance of considering such nuances in attachment studies.

Utilizing interferometry analysis, we scrutinized the synthesized silica wafers and uncovered a uniform distribution of pores. Based on the modeling approach, the regions between the pores experienced the highest shear stress, surpassing 1.8 Pa, with wafers featuring pore depths exceeding 135 nm exhibiting a more pronounced pattern (Figure 7).

Figure 7: **A** - Schematic representation of the chamber used in the research (side view) **B** - Combined image of fluorescently-labeled cells of *S. epidermidis* DSM20044 attached to the surface of silica wafer with 260nm deep pores.

The results of PCA brought forth key determinants influencing bacterial attachment patterns (Figure 8). The bacterial morphology and ionic strength of the solution emerged as crucial factors shaping these interactions. Specifically, cocci-shaped cells exhibited a robust positive correlation with the speed of the flow, while rod-shaped cells showcased a correlation with the surface roughness. These relationships highlight the complex nature of bacterial attachment, where distinct cell morphologies respond differently to environmental factors.

Figure 8: PCA analysis illustrating the impact of key factors, including the number of attached cells (count_mean), depths of the wafer pores (roughness), and speed of flow (speed), on bacterial cell attachment. Samples are color-coded based on their association with specific wafer types, providing a visual representation of the intricate relationship between surface characteristics, solution conditions, and bacterial attachment patterns. Confidence ellipses enhance the interpretation of data distribution, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the nuanced interplay observed in the experimental results.

Despite minor variations in attachment patterns on wafers ranging from 30 to 260 nm in depth, a significant shift occurred when the silica wafer pores reached a depth of 0.5 μm . Remarkably, the number of attached cells increased drastically at this threshold, irrespective of bacterial morphology and ionic strength of the solution. This pivotal depth represents a critical point influencing bacterial attachment behavior, shedding light on a key determinant in the interplay between bacterial cells and surfaces. This is particularly important when we plan to populate planar surface or surface with highly porous surfaces such as flat electrodes or brush type electrodes. Similar, the type of root of plants with either high brush like structures or more smooth roots can on one hand physically stimulate better attachment or on other hand prevent attachment of cells, respectively. Another factor is the shape of cells where cocci type cells should better attach on the flow through system such as water purification and bacillary type of shapes can be used more when in combination of the flow also highly porous surfaces are used. These insights will have important implications when the synthetic polymicrobial structures will be attached either on roots, BES electrodes or on carriers and will be important that in prior of the application, the characteristics of the cell shape of the strains get match with the physical properties of the system where the cells will be attached.

2.2.2 Impact of hydrophilicity on the biomass attachment

Understanding the role of hydrophilicity in bacterial attachment to surfaces is crucial for deciphering the dynamics of biomass growth and dissipation. This is especially important in the case of graphite surface

that will be used in the BES electrodes and it is very well known as a model type for hydrophobic surface and can represent certain obstacle in structuring biofilms on the surface (Liu and Li, 2017). In this investigation, we explored the influence of hydrophilicity on the attachment dynamics, growth, and dissipation of bacterial biomass from environmental samples. Our study focused on the interaction of this biomass with the surface of porous carriers treated with cold plasma, a technique that is oxidizing the elements exposed on the surface of the material and in the most cases it transforms the hydrophobic surfaces in more hydrophilic. Another aim of this activity was also that we developed microscopy methods for following and evaluation of biofilm formations on both, porous and smooth surfaces, representing difficult and simple samples regarding the measuring biofilm formations, respectively. These developed methods and our observations using microscopy methods can be then applied either for evaluating electrodes, carriers or root surfaces.

2.2.2.1 Methodology

The experimental investigation concentrated on exploring the interaction between bacterial cells and surfaces with diverse wettability characteristics. The study employed environmental samples enriched with natural microbiota derived from a Slovenian wastewater treatment plant. At this level, in the process of development of methods, we used microbially rich water from waste water treatment plant and we did not use isolated consortia in T1.3 to avoid their deterioration during the manipulation. The isolated consortia in T1.3 will be used in the following period after the selection and further increase of the biomass. The water used here was the most appropriate since the amount of microbes is high and the community resemble those bacteria that are naturally involved in degradation of various pollutants.

To ensure sufficient biomass at the stationary phase, a 1% v/v inoculum of the natural sample underwent overnight cultivation in minimal media M9 with 2% glucose as the sole carbon source. The bacterial cells were subjected to three washes with sterile 0.9% NaCl solution through centrifugation at 5000 g for 5 minutes (Eppendorf MiniSpin). Normalization of cell suspensions to $OD_{600nm} = 0.1$ was achieved using a 96-well microtiter plate reader (SynergyH4, Biotek). For visualization purposes, the cultured cells were stained with Syto 11 fluorescent dye (Invitrogen) following the manufacturer's guidelines.

As a model surface, commercial biofilm carriers (Mutag Biochip™, Multi Umwelttechnologie AG, Germany), constructed from porous polyethylene, were employed to evaluate the impact of surface hydrophilicity. The carriers underwent exposure to two distinct regimes (E-mode and H-mode, more and less intensive treatment, respectively) of low-pressure oxygen plasma. The assessment of sedimentation efficiency utilized a growth chamber setup detailed in section 2.2.1.2 of this report (Figure 7A).

During the experimental procedure, a 20 μ L volume of stained bacterial suspension was gently applied dropwise onto the surface of the biofilm carriers within the growth chamber. Following a 30-minute undisturbed incubation at room temperature and in the absence of direct light, non-adherent cells were meticulously washed away with 100 μ L of MilliQ water. Subsequently, 200 μ L of fresh sterile M9 media were introduced into the chamber. The assembled chamber, sealed with a coverslip, was inverted to counteract gravitational settling, and the sample was maintained at 30 °C in the dark. Image acquisition was performed using an inverted fluorescent microscope (Zeiss Axio Observer Z1), equipped with a Plan-Neofluar 40x/0.6 objective lens, GFP (485 nm/528 nm) filter set, and the Orca digital CCD camera.

2.2.2.2 Results

The microscopic observation of bacterial cell attachment to surfaces with different hydrophilic properties revealed distinctive behaviors during the attachment process. The untreated surface exhibited numerous bacterial clumps separated by significant distances (Figure 9 A). In contrast, the E-mode

treated surface displayed a uniform coverage with individual bacterial cells (Figure 9B). On the other hand, the H-mode treated surface exhibited an intermediate pattern, characterized by both aggregated bacterial clumps and a considerable number of individual cells (Figure 9C).

Figure 9: Microscopic observation of bacterial attachment on surfaces with different hydrophilicity. **A** - Untreated control surface. **B** - E-mode treated surface. **C** - H-mode treated surface.

Figure 10: Quantitative analysis of bacterial attachment on surfaces. **A** - Number of attached events. **B** - Average size of attached cells. **C** - Area occupied by attached cells.

To quantify these observed patterns, three key parameters were assessed and presented in the plots (Figure 10): the number of events (Figure 10A), the average size of cells (Figure 10B) and the area occupied by cells (Figure 10C). The average size of cells is an imaginary value representing continuous signal and does not resemble the real cell size. The numerical evaluation and statistical analysis aligned with the microscopic observations. The hydrophobic control surfaces exhibited a five-fold decrease in the number of cells compared to the treated surfaces. Furthermore, the average size of cells on hydrophobic surfaces was 1 μm larger than those on E-mode surfaces and 0.5 μm larger than those on H-mode surfaces. These findings provide numerical confirmation of the microscopic observations, highlighting the substantial impact of surface treatment on bacterial cell attachment, with treated surfaces demonstrating enhanced coverage and individual cell distribution.

These results showed important information that will be needed in the further steps of formation of synthetic biofilm structures within the BIOSYSMO. Specifically, the hydrophobic surface of graphite based anodes can represent obstacle for attachment of bacteria since hydrophobic nature of this material might decrease the efficiency of procedures. By the plasma treatments we can stimulate attachment. In addition, the quantitative methods for determining efficiencies of attachment developed within the scope of the BIOSYSMO project we are also capable of estimating the attractiveness of the surface for microbial attachment that is important evaluation procedure to evaluate efficiencies of microbial activities.

3 Subtask 3.2.2 - Development of electroactive biofilms

3.1 Preparing electrogenic core-shell structures from microbial consortia by aggregation

Based on the knowledge acquired from the iACME isolation techniques described in D1.2 and encapsulation protocols detailed in Section 2.1, we selected two distinct electrogenic consortia from sampling Sites 6 and 7. These consortia underwent a characterization process to evaluate their capacity for vanadate reduction, serving as a proxy for electrogenic activity in the subsequent stages of the study. Since we are preparing two niche systems, one aerobic that will be on the surface and another anaerobic within the core of the core shell structure, we incubated consortia in aerobic and anaerobic conditions. These two specialized consortia will be then used in the further experiments to engineer either biofilms or aggregates with a core-shell structure.

3.1.1 Methodology

The enrichment through aggregation and vanadate reduction of the isolated electrogenic bacterial consortia was executed for the designated samples with distinctive characteristics (Table 2), following a well-defined protocol established for the iACME approach, as elaborated in D1.2. The selection of samples for the isolation was based on results of molecular characteristics of samples where samples with higher content of DNA and bigger bacterial diversity were selected during the activity of T1.3 and reported in D1.2). We focused in degradation of PAHs that served as a carbon source.

Table 2: Samples used for the isolation of electrogenic consortia

Sampling site	Type of sample	Target contaminant
Site 6 8062	water	Metals (Mn, Fe, Al, As)
Site 7 PZ-19b	groundwater	Hydrocarbons including PAH (e.g. naphthalene)

400 mL of each sample underwent sequential filtration through 20 and 0.2 µm filters utilizing a vacuum pump. The collected biomass was then washed off the filters with a 0.9% saline solution. The obtained fraction underwent initial characterization for physical properties, including surface charge and electrophoretic mobility, using an electrophoretic light scattering (ELS) device. Subsequently, the available biomass was quantified using flow cytometry, incorporating fluorescent labeling for precise identification.

Building upon insights gained from experiments detailed in Section 2.1.1 of this report, bacterial aggregates were constructed, and the efficacy of aggregation was determined by flow cytometry methods. These constructed aggregates were then inoculated into minimal media containing 3.8 mM of V₂O₅ and a 50 µM mixture of two selected recalcitrant polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), namely, pyrene and benzo[a]pyrene, as a sole carbon source.

Cultivation occurred under two distinct conditions: (i) aerated conditions with constant agitation at 140 rpm and 28°C, and (ii) under anaerobic atmosphere comprising 85% N₂, 10% CO₂, and 5% H₂ without agitation. Evaluation of vanadium removal efficiency was conducted using the DPC approach, as described in Section 2.1.1. Vanadyl content measurements were performed after 6 days of cultivation. Subsequently, after 8 days of cultivation, biomass was harvested and underwent another round of electrostatic modification using the same polymers. Constructed aggregates were then reinoculated into fresh V containing media, and reduction efficiency was measured against an abiotic control. At the end of the cultivation period, 10 µL of the sample was aliquoted and aggregates as well as planktonic cells visually checked using the light microscopy at a 40x magnification.

3.1.2 Results

Surface property analysis of the cell-particle fractions among the samples unveiled a strong negative charge, and electrophoretic mobility of -35.5 mV and -2.77×10^{-4} cm/s² for sampling Site 7 and -16.1 mV and -1.26×10^{-4} cm/s² for sampling Site 6 (Figure 11). Size distribution analysis indicated that the majority of particles in the planktonic form of the isolated fractions measured below 1 μ m, with events ranging from 2 to 9 μ m constituting approximately 20% of the population. Upon the application of aggregation protocols, the share of aggregated events for the fraction obtained from Site 6 (S6_Aggregated on Figure 12) increased by 9%. In contrast, the aggregation protocols applied to the sample isolated from Site 7 showed no significant change in sample composition.

Figure 11: Surface characteristics of filtrated cell-particle fractions: **A** - zeta potential, **B** - Electrophoretic mobility

Figure 12: Distribution of sizes in filtrated cell-particle fraction

Fluorescent labeling of biomass using nucleic acid dyes revealed that the microbial fraction from Site 7 was richer in biomass than those observed in Site 6, with percentages of 67.8% and 29.2%, respectively (Figure 13). This discrepancy is correlated with the type of contamination, as Site 6 reported a lower concentration of carbon sources.

Figure 13: Results of determination of presence of biomass in filtrated cell-particle fraction, based on fluorescent labeling of nucleic acids

Aggregate formation results demonstrated that the application of the developed protocols increased the number of events expressing fluorescent signals from both encapsulated and non-encapsulated cells by 3% for Sample Site 6 and by a notable 28% for Sample Site 7 (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Efficiency of aggregation procedure after large aggregates separation and measuring by flow cytometry method. The results are based on gating of the fluorescent events, expressing both green and red signals from encapsulated and non-encapsulated cells.

Vanadium-reducing activity measurements demonstrated that all isolated fractions exhibited the capability to reduce vanadium, with distinct activity levels observed between samples and cultivation conditions. While the amount of reduced V was twofold higher in anaerobic conditions compared to aerated conditions for both samples, the difference between the samples from Sampling site 6 and sampling site 7 was not statistically significant. Notably, the re-aggregation of harvested biomass led to an improvement in reduction efficiency for all cultivation conditions (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: Efficiency of V reduction by artificial aggregates after 6 days of cultivation. Both, aerobic and anaerobic conditions were used for the isolation. 2 passages were performed with repeated aggregation protocols to improve the efficiency of V5+ reduction.

Figure 16: Microscopic images of bacterial aggregates at 6th day of cultivation. (a) - Aggregate obtained from Sampling site 6 and cultivated in aerated conditions, (b) - Aggregate obtained from Sampling site 6 and cultivated in anaerobic atmosphere, (c) - Aggregate obtained from Sampling site 7 and cultivated in aerated conditions, (d) - Aggregate obtained from Sampling site 7 and cultivated in anaerobic atmosphere. Reduced vanadate particles displayed as black nontransparent dots.

Microscopic observations further validated the V^{5+} removal processes, revealing the formation of solid precipitates represented as black, non-transparent dots. Samples cultivated in anaerobic conditions exhibited bacterial aggregates of larger size with a higher quantity of precipitates bearing inside, emphasizing the influence of cultivation conditions on aggregate characteristics and V-removal efficiency (Figure 16).

In the further experiments those two fractions of aggregates will be combined in formation of core, from anaerobic aggregates, and shell, from aerobic aggregates resulting in core-shell structure that will be tested for metal removal and PAH degradation. The stimulation of PAH degradation using BES system will be also further investigated.

3.2 Estimating suitability of using polyelectrolytes for deposition of cells on electrodes

In above described preparation of microbial structures (see section 3.1) we were aiming to apply synthetic polycellular microbial structures on the surface of electrodes using polyelectrolytes. As the close interaction of bacteria with the electrode surfaces is a pivotal property for the development and optimization of full-scale BES, we developed a bioassay to determine the interaction of selected polyelectrolytes and electrode conductive surfaces. As a model system, here we used a photo induced system that generates extremely low currents which was coupled with biological water splitting process using photosynthetic organisms. This was selected to determine the effects of polyelectrolytes interference with the electron flow from biological systems to the electrodes. The effects on the electron transfers were then tested using linear voltammetry. Since we used another type of cells to determine these above mentioned effects we also needed to determine if we could observe any toxic effects of the

electrode material or polyelectrolytes on our biological systems. For this purpose to determine toxicity of the system components, surface material and polyelectrolytes we used the same methodology as described above and we could not see any toxic effects on the selected photosynthetically active cells.

3.2.1 Methodology

Covering the micro-sized semiconductors: Since BiVO_4 microparticles and cyanobacterial cell have negative surface charge, cellular adhesion will not be adequate. To overcome this challenge and improve the adhesion, the surface of microparticles has been covered by AcetPEI polymer and cell adhesion investigated using flow cytometry. To do that, Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) dye was diluted in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at a concentration of 1 mg/ml. 5 mg of conductive microparticles were added to 1 mL of the dye solution and stirred on a shaker for 20 min. Then the particles were washed twice with 0.9% NaCl solution to remove excess dye. 5 mg of stained particles were placed for 3 minutes in an ultrasound bath to break up the conglomerates. Next, 5 mg of stained particles were mixed with a 0.25% solution of AcetPEI. The test tube with the particles was mounted on the shaker for 20 minutes. After that, the particles were precipitated using a centrifuge for 3 min, 1000 ppm. The supernatant was removed and the particles were washed with 0.9% NaCl solution. 5 mg/L of coated BiVO_4 particles and non-coated (as a control) were mixed with *Synechococcus elongatus* 2973 (Sy73) with $\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}} = 2$. The test tube with the particles was mounted on the shaker for 20 minutes. The cell attachment and viability has been studied by flow cytometry.

3.2.2 Results

To determine the smallest effect on the flow of electrons from biological system to the electrode, albeit their separation by polyelectrolytes for approximately 2nm to 4nm after polymer coating of electrodes or cells the electrodes must be well coated with cells to have optimal results in this bioassay. The number of events in the case of free cells, coated particles with polymers and cells attached particles has been studied using flow cytometry. The free cells value for control were detected 24.7% while coated particles with polymers showed 1.4%. It can be concluded that since AcetPEI has positive surface charge it can cover the microparticles of BiVO_4 with negative surface charges which led to significant enhancement in cellular adhesion.

The PEI coated electrodes were then exposed to the light where the photocatalytic reaction is expected. The linear voltammetry approach for BiVO_4 and P25 (commercial form of TiO_2) coated electrodes on Fluorine-doped Tin Oxide (FTO) glass with additional layer of PEI in 0.1 M NaCl solution was used as the electrolyte, showed no statistical difference in three-electrode systems with Ag/AgCl and Pt as the reference and counter electrodes, respectively (Figure 17), indicating that polyelectrolytes can be used for coating cells or electrodes in the BES approach.

Figure 17: Effects of polymers on the activity of the BES system.

3.3 Design of the custom-made BES setup

As a result of inter-partnership visits between LEITAT and JSI, a custom-designed BES was engineered and the methods for electrochemical analysis has been implemented. Here we will describe the prototype for our experiments that will be further used. The main aim of this system is that we can combine microscopy studies with the BES approach to (i) determine efficiency of biofilm structuring using electrostatics, (ii) efficiency of BES, (iii) enabling us to study biofilm succession and (iv) to control local environment either through headspace addition of gas or by dosage of the nutrients. In this regards we designed a main chamber that can host 6 anodes enabling two triplicates for experiments with the deposited synthetic biofilms. The BES system is coupled with the air-type cathode (see Figure 18). The designed system was then 3D printed using a polylactic acid polymer amended with the polyhydroxybutyrate (Figure 19, Figure 20).

Figure 18: Scheme of 3D reconstruction of main chamber, cathode gasket and cover with holes for delivering pipes for control of the gas or nutrient status.

Figure 19: The 3D printed BES prototype for biofilm structuring and succession experiments: Main chamber with attached anodes

Figure 20: 3D printed assembled chamber for testing. In front the air-type cathode is assembled.

3.4 Modulation of redox potential on electrodes

LEITAT developed different protocols based on the modulation of the redox potential to increase efficiency of selection and attachment of electrogenic strain on electrodes. The initial samples before the procedures and then formed biofilms on electrodes by the approach developed by LEITAT have been analysed in order to (i) determine succession of the community, (ii) select and isolate electrogenic strains and (iii) to correlate between community structure and electrogenic activities (Aulenta et al., 2011).

The development of the protocols was done once confirmed the sampling availability of all sites considering the update done in 2023. The sampling-list has been updated and, subsequently the development of electroactive biofilms for the treatment of each sample has started. In this section the different protocols used to develop each type of biofilm considering the expected pollutant removal pathways are described as well as the main results achieved until this date.

3.4.1 Biofilm for metals removal

The bioelectrochemical system which will be used in WP4 for heavy metals removal (BES-M) will treat groundwater from the well w8101 from Site 6 (see D1.1).

The BES-M reactor consists in a multi-chamber electrochemical cell. In this case, the microorganisms in the biofilm will not be directly treating the metal-contaminated groundwater. However, their electroactivity will supply electrons to the cathode where the metals removal will take place thanks to different reduction reactions. Different removal pathways have been identified under similar conditions such as direct metals reduction and indirect byproduct precipitation through metal hydroxides (Song et al., 2019) or metal oxides (Wang et al., 2017). Hence, the operation of these reactors do not require the isolation of microorganisms capable to precipitate or immobilize metals contained in the groundwater. In this case, the biofilm will be fed with a carbon source (biodegradable organic matter) contained in a

synthetic media or wastewater. To accomplish their role, microorganisms will catalyze the oxidation of this organic matter by respiration delivering the electrons produced to a solid electrode, the anode in this case, to be later delivered to the cathode by an external electric circuit. Thus, in this phase the objective is to develop an electroactive biofilm capable to degrade organic matter.

3.4.1.1. Methods

The anodes inoculation reactor consisted in flat plate reactors with polymethylmethacrylate chambers. Each reactor allocates two stacks of electrodes connected in parallel (Figure 21B), i.e. 2 anodes and 2 air-cathodes of 100 cm² of surface each one. The anode material used is battery grade carbon felt (Sigracell® KFD2.5, from SGL carbon). The air-cathodes material was unidirectional carbon fibers (SGL Carbon) with an oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) catalyst (2 mg/cm² of PMF-011904 catalyst from Pajarito Powder) embedded between two layers of different types of Tyvek® textile (DuPont) as can be observed in Figure 21 A. The current collectors were 316 stainless steel frames for the cathodes and isostatic graphite (PV15 from SGL Carbon) frames for the anodes.

Figure 21: A) Air-cathode scheme; B) Inoculation reactor scheme.

The inoculum of this reactor was concentrated biomass, containing a mixture (consortium) of microorganisms, from a long-term operating microbial fuel cell which was initially inoculated using activated sludge from a wastewater treatment plant almost 9 years ago.

The reactor was hydraulically connected to a buffer tank and the medium was circulated through the reactor by means of a peristaltic pump. The medium of the reactor was replaced each week with 3.5 L of mineral medium to ensure that the biomass has sufficient carbon source. The mineral medium contained NaHCO₃ 8.4 g/L, NaCH₃COO 2.5 g/L, NaCl 0.45g/L, MgCl₂·6H₂O 0.165 g/L, K₂HPO₄ 0.128 g/L, NH₄Cl 0.0495 g/L, Mg₂SO₄ 0.0153 g/L, CaCl₂ 0.0136 g/L and Wolfe vitamins.

The protocol used with this aim is based on the modulation of the electrode potential to promote the selection of those microorganisms capable of exchanging electrons with this solid electrode, i.e.

electroactive bacteria. In this case, a potential gradient from -0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl until -0.35 V vs Ag/AgCl is applied to the anode in -0.05 V potential steps which lasts 79 h (each one).

The protocol also includes electrochemical characterization techniques between potential steps such as open circuit voltammetry (OCV) and cyclic voltammetry (CV, from -0.1 V until -0.6 V vs Ag/AgCl with a scan rate of 10 mV/s). The reactors are electrochemically controlled by means of a potentiostat (VMP3 from BioLogic).

The subsequent inoculation batches will be also monitored analyzing the following parameters: chemical oxygen demand (COD) (using Kits from Hach Lange), pH and electric conductivity (using multimeter HQ40D from Hach Lange)

3.4.1.2. Results

To inoculate all the anodes necessary for the BES reactors for metals removal (BES-M), different inoculation batches with the inoculation reactor described before are needed. In Figure 22 are shown the two inoculation reactors which are being used for the anodes inoculation for BES-M development.

Figure 22: Operating anode inoculation reactors for BES-M.

The 1st batch current density evolution during the chronoamperometry and the applied potential to the anodes vs Ag/AgCl is presented in Figure 23 A. As can be observed the anodes performed significant electroactivity already in the early days of the inoculation (Figure 23A). This way, in the second step when -150 mV vs Ag/AgCl were applied, 0.59 A/m² were produced, and in the 3rd step applying -200 mV the current density reached 2.08 A/m². The significant amount of inoculum (coming from an operating electroactive reactor) used, which was distributed through the surface of the bare carbon felt before assembling the reactor, may explain this quick electroactive response. After this, the current density decreased significantly in the 4th potential step until 0.15 A/m² and, also, in the subsequent step where it was maintained around 0.18 A/m². This kind of behavior is usually attributed to the more severe selection conditions that were applied in the new potential step. This usually represents a reduction of the electroactivity until the electroactive bacteria in the biofilm is adapted to the new conditions. The current density increased significantly in the following cycles reaching a maximum of 2.53 A/m² in the 7

th step. These electroactive biofilms are considered inoculated when performed a stable current density higher than 1.5 A/m² for more than 7 days in the last potential step (-350mV vs Ag/AgCl).

Figure 23: A) Chronoamperometry of the inoculation of two electroactive anodes. B) Cyclic voltammetry after 6th (blue) and 7th (red) potential step.

In Figure 23B is shown the current output in cyclic voltammetry after different inoculation steps. This way, after the 7th inoculation step, i.e. -350 mV vs Ag/AgCl, the reactor was performing higher current in the range where BES-M reactors are expected to work (between -200 mV and -400 mV) indicating that the electroactivity increased and, subsequently, indicating that the biofilm is more active and well-established.

As can be observed in Figure 24 the OCV measured after each inoculation step followed a decreasing trend until reaching almost -430 mV. This means that the potential between anode and cathode was bigger after each potential step. As the cathode is abiotic, what is expected is that its potential remains stable in OCV tests. Hence, the anode potential in open circuit has been decreasing during the inoculation what is also an indicator of the increase of the electroactivity of an anode.

Figure 24: OCV of the reactor after each applied potential step during the inoculation.

Samples of the grown biofilms were taken and sent to JSI to be analyzed for microbial community parameters as well as further enriched of electrogenic bacteria using aggregation approach. The results will be presented in D3.6. Data from physicochemical analysis and the subsequent inoculation batches will be also presented in D3.6.

3.4.2. Biofilms for HC removal

The bioelectrochemical system which is going to be used in WP4 for hydrocarbon degradation (BES-HC) will treat groundwater from Pz-39 from Site 7 (see D1.1).

Petroleum hydrocarbons (HC) are complex pollutants, composed by a mixture of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons. The bioremediation of groundwater polluted with HC requires a microbial consortia with multiple microorganisms each one degrading specific hydrocarbons. These microorganisms can grow on HC as sole carbon and energy source, but they need oxygen as final electron acceptor of the HC degradation. This is one important limiting factor in contaminated groundwater as it is usually under anoxic conditions. However, the electrodes, in this case the anodes, can be used by microorganisms to deliver these electrons produced acting as electron acceptor despite the anoxic conditions. The selection of electroactive-bacteria from the polluted site could be advantageous for the electro-bioremediation, as these bacteria are already adapted to the physicochemical characteristics of the water matrix. An analysis of electro-bioremediation literature, regarding anodic treatment of hydrocarbons contaminated groundwater, revealed that high anode potentials (+497 mV vs SHE) are needed for TPH/BTEX/PAH oxidation (Pous Rodríguez et al., 2018). These potentials can be reached easily using a MEC configuration, i.e. applying an external voltage to the BES reactors.

3.4.2.1. Methods

Single-chamber air-cathode BES reactors (300 mL volume, VidraFoc), from now on BES-HC, will be used with this aim. The anode material consists of graphite fibers brush (20 cm², Mill-Rose, USA). The cathode is composed by 12,6 cm² of unidirectional carbon fibers (SGL carbon) with ORR catalyst (2 mg/cm² of PMF-011904 catalyst from Pajarito Powder).

For the inoculation of BES reactors, the protocol used is based in the isolation protocol presented in D1.2. However, it has been modified for the formation of the electroactive biofilms: it is decided to discard the kerosene addition with the aim to promote the growth of indigenous bacteria in closer to real conditions in terms of availability of the different types of carbon source available. Thus, in this case, the reactors are electrochemically operated in 3 electrodes configuration too, controlling the anode potential at 0.6 vs Ag/AgCl. This will promote the growth of electroactive biomass.

The inoculation of the reactors is also monitored with periodical electrochemical characterization through cyclic voltammetry (CV; scan rate 10 mV/s; range -0.6 V - +0.8 V) and OCV techniques). The reactors are electrochemically controlled by means of a potentiostat (VMP3 from BioLogic).

The inoculation will be also monitored analyzing the following parameters: COD (using Kits from Hach Lange), pH and electric conductivity (using multimeter HQ40D from Hach Lange) and HC and BTEX content will be analyzed using the protocols K and L described in D1.1 respectively.

3.4.2.2. Results

As can be observed in Figure 25, 6 new reactors have been constructed and are ready to be inoculated.

Figure 25: BEC-HC reactors

The current density evolution as well as CV and OCV data from the inoculation phase will be presented and discussed in D3.6. Also, samples of the grown biomass in the reactors will be taken and sent to JSI to be analysed for microbial community parameters.

3.4.3. Biofilms for Chlorinated Ethenes removal

The bioelectrochemical system which will be used in WP4 for chlorinated compounds removal will treat groundwater from the wells Pz-43, Pz-53, Pz-52, Pz-62, Pz-63 from Site 9 and wells Pz-12 from Site 14 (new site in Nuremberg, Germany).

As a preliminary step, microbial community analysis will be performed on the groundwater samples to evaluate the presence of organohalide respiring bacteria (OHRB), which are known to perform the anaerobic reductive dechlorination process utilizing electron donors (i.e. hydrogen) (Dell'Armi et al., 2022). Among the OHRB, *Dehalococcoides mccartyi* is the only one that can completely reduce chlorinated compounds such as perchloroethylene (PCE), vinyl chloride (VC), and trichloroethylene (TCE), to ethene (Löffler et al., 2013). At the same time, in literature are reported the specialized genes encoding for the reductive dehalogenases (i.e. *TceA*, *BvcA*, *VcrA*) (Dell'Armi et al., 2022) and the genes involved in the oxidative dichlorination (Mattes et al., 2015). Therefore, the expression of such genes and the presence of *D. mccartyi* are reported to be valuable biomarkers for the dechlorination process (Dell'Armi et al., 2022).

3.4.3.1. Methods

Aiming to have an inoculum source for BES reactors, the first step is to establish a procedure for the cultivation of an active biomass of dechlorinative microorganisms. For this purpose, the recently received groundwater samples will be used as microorganisms' source and will be incubated at room temperature in Schott bottles in aerobic and anaerobic conditions, adding lactate and acetate as additional carbon and electron sources if needed. For the anaerobic cultivation, the gas phase will be composed of 80% H₂ and 20% CO₂. Microbial community analysis will be performed on the final

inoculum source, to be able to identify shift in the biodiversity due to the biomass enrichment on the electrodes of the BES

The following step would be to perform a biomass enrichment on both electrodes of a bioelectrochemical system, to select and increase the amount of the specialized bacteria responsible for the reductive/oxidative dechlorination pathways. At the anode, oxygen evolution will take place. Here, the aim is to enrich for microorganisms capable of aerobically oxidizing chlorinated compounds with longer carbon chains ($>C_2$), utilizing the produced oxygen, resulting in the formation of CO_2 and chlorinated ethanes (i.e. TCE, PCE, VC) which can then be reduced to ethane in the cathodic compartment. At the cathode, hydrogen evolution will take place in anaerobic conditions. is to select and enrich the cathodic surface with OHRB capable of utilizing the produced hydrogen as electron donor for their metabolism, while utilizing chlorinated compounds as electron acceptor, resulting in the substitution of the chlorine atoms present in the chlorinated molecules with protons. As mentioned beforehand, *D. mccartyi* is the only known microbes capable of completely reducing TCE, PCE and VC to ethane. Therefore, its selection and enrichment on the electrode surface would result in highly performing dechlorinative biocathodes.

A flat-plate electrolysis cell made of polymethylmethacrylate with an open electrode surface of 100 cm^2 will be built up. The reactors will be operated in batch mode with the real groundwater samples, continuously recirculating the liquid in the cell utilizing a peristaltic pump and a buffer tank. The cell will be controlled at a cell voltage of 1.5-3 V with a commercial power source. A PicoLog datalogger will be used to record the current achieved in the system. Titanium wire and titanium rods will be used as the current collector, while stainless steel wool, carbon felt, and granular carbon (i.e. biochar) will be evaluated as possible electrode materials. Regarding the biofilm formation, from the literature it appears that, even though electroactivity has been proved for microorganisms performing anaerobic reductive dechlorination (Liu et al., 2013) the chlorinated compounds removal rate is higher in presence of hydrogen evolution (Aulenta et al., 2011). For this reason, the electrode surface serves more as a growth support for microbes, aimed at maximizing the triple-phase boundary between microbes, contaminated water and gaseous phase (hydrogen / oxygen). In this sense, the biofilm formation and attachment will be dependent on the specific biocompatibility of the electrode material and the gas phase evolution rate, which, if too high, would result in the detachment of biofilm from the electrode surface due to the sheer force of the bubbles produced. For example, Zeppilli et al., 2024 operated a reactor for tetrachloroethane removal utilizing mixed-metal oxides anodes inserted into a bed of silica beads, which served as biofilm support. Our systems will be inoculated utilizing the same biomass contained in the contaminated groundwater, recirculating the water in batch mode tracking the degradation of the chlorinated compounds, and exchanging the groundwater when the degradation of compounds will be completed. The developed biofilm performances will be evaluated by the chlorinated compounds removal rate, as well as the hydrogen/oxygen uptake.

3.4.3.2. Results

Sample sites and piezometers were selected, based on the most promising chemical composition. Groundwater polluted with chlorinated ethenes samples just have arrived at LEITAT. The groundwater samples are currently being analysed to identify and quantify the chlorinated compounds in the sample. For this purpose, an analytical method based on gas chromatography (GC) and subsequent electron capture detection (ECD) is being developed. Gas chromatography is an analytical method where a mixture of component (analyte) is injected in a column filled with a chemical component, called “stationary phase”, and separated in single components based on their affinity for the stationary phase, and, therefore, the time necessary for the component to exit the column (retention time). The single

components are then identified and quantified utilizing an ECD, which is a type of detector specifically designed for the analysis of highly electronegative molecules, such as chlorinated compounds. Here, the different compounds determine a signal proportional to the number of chlorine atoms in the molecule. The component will then be identified by comparing its retention time and signal to known standards of selected compounds. GC-ECD allows for the routine quantification of chlorinated hydrocarbons, tracking the compounds' evolution in time and quantifying intermediate compounds, produced due to a partial reductive/oxidative dechlorination process. The developed protocol and the characterization of the groundwater will be updated in the pertinent deliverables.

4 Conclusions

In the recent work the main aims were towards development of methods and to determine parameters that might limit attachment, stability, and performance of polymicrobial synthetic structures. Based on our insights through these experiments within the activities related to T3.2.1 bacterial shapes are important contributors for efficient attachment in either in high flow through system or when exposed to high surface area where coccal or bacillary shapes are predominating, respectively. In addition, the surface hydrophilicity is important factor for attachment of microbes and the most convenient method using cold plasma treatment was shown to overcome the attachment inhibition.

By development of the methods for formation of aggregated structures and investigation of metal precipitation properties we determined that the structure stabilities are dependant on the nutrient source and physical perturbations such as shaking. The developed methods and incubation conditions were developed and can be applied on the BIOSYSMO selected consortia. In these experiments using model organism the metal precipitation under aerobic conditions has been also shown and can be stimulated by formation of aggregated microbial structures.

Related to the T3.2.2 JSI determined that using polyelectrolytes can be suitable for formation of synthetic biofilms on anodes in BES systems since it has been shown that does not interfere with the electron flow from the biological systems. In order to further proceed with the electrode modifications and monitoring of biofilms the BES setup enabling biofilm studies has been designed and first prototype prepared.

LEITAT developed different biofilm growth protocols, based on the electrochemical potential modulation, have been defined for the treatment of different polluted groundwaters selected in WP1 (Site 6, Site 7, Site 9 & Site 14). It was done according to the requirements of pollutant degradation/removal pathways expected in each case.

Two biofilm inoculation reactors have been designed and constructed for the planar bio-anodes which are going to be used in task 4.4 (WP4) for metals removal in BES-M reactors. Two anodes have been successfully inoculated presenting appropriate OCV and also appropriate current density at the operation potential range. The inoculation of the rest of the anodes is ongoing.

Four reactors have been designed and constructed for 3D bio-anodes inoculation (carbon brushes) which are going to be used in task 4.4 (WP4) for Hydrocarbon removal in BES-HC reactors.

Flat plate reactor has been designed and is being constructed as a chlorinated ethenes degrading bacteria source. After the cultivation in Schott bottles the microorganisms grown in this reactor will be transferred to the final reactor (BES-CE) in task 4.4 (WP4) for chlorinated ethenes removal in BES-M reactors.

5 Planned work for the second period

The upcoming phases of our work will focus on the following key objectives:

1. **Metagenomic Analysis:** Conducting a comprehensive metagenomic analysis to unravel the structure of metal precipitation aggregates (JSI).
2. **Core-Shell Structures for PAH Degradation:** Developing and assessing core-shell structures for the qualitative and quantitative determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) degradation (JSI).
3. **Spatial Distribution Characterization:** Investigating the spatial distribution of consortia to evaluate their efficiency in PAH degradation. This involves determining genomic structure, transcriptome, and metabolic transformation during the succession of structures, particularly in relation to Work Package 2 (WP2) (JSI in collaboration with IDENER).
4. **Starting up inoculating electrodes in BES reactors** as a source of electroactive bacteria and CE degrading bacteria (JSI in collaboration with LEITAT).
5. **Electrogenic biofilms development:** Different biofilm development strategies based on the electrochemical potential modulation will be applied on each reactor type depending on the pollutant targeted in task 4.4 (WP4). The electroactivity of the biofilm will be electrochemically characterized to generate comparable data. (LEITAT)
6. **Electrogenic Biofilm Analysis:** Analyzing electrogenic biofilms obtained from operational Bioelectrochemical Systems (BES) to isolate electrogenic strains. These strains will serve as fundamental building blocks for structuring biofilms on BES electrodes, specifically for the degradation of PAHs and chlorinated ethenes (JSI).
7. **Spatial Distribution of Electrogenic Bacteria:** Determining the placement and spatial distribution of electrogenic and non-electrogenic bacteria. This investigation aims to understand how these factors influence the efficiency of electrogenicity evolution (JSI in collaboration with LEITAT).
8. **Electrode Modifications for BES Efficiency:** Utilizing insights gained from electrode modifications outlined in this deliverable to enhance Bioelectrochemical System efficiency and prolong the operational time (JSI in collaboration with LEITAT).

These objectives collectively form the next steps in our research, allowing us to delve deeper into the intricate processes of metal precipitation, PAH degradation, and the dynamics of electrogenic biofilms for improved BES efficiency.

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